

MSBMD
Metallic System
Builder for Molecular
Dynamics – An
OpenMD-based
software for
Simulating Gold
Nanostructures

A chemical leap into
molecular dynamics

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01

Project Manager

04

Analysis

02

Builder

05

Additional
settings

03

Molecular
Dynamics

06

XYZEditor

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01

Project Manager

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Project Manager

Open a MSBMD project

Create a MSBMD project

Close an opened MSBMD project

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Project Manager: New action

Project Manager: Open action

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Project Manager: Open action

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Builder: Option list

Table 1. Builder list and its description.

<u>Advanced nanoparticles</u>	Builds core-shell nanoparticles with custom molar fraction or vacancy.
<u>Convert structure</u>	Exchanges between OpenMD-supported data file format.
<u>Dissolve solute</u>	Dissolves a solute into waterbox.
<u>Icosahedral nanoparticles</u>	Builds an icosahedral, decahedral, cuboctahedron, etc.
<u>Nanoparticles</u>	Builds nanoparticles of some transition elements.
<u>Nanoparticle with vacancy</u>	A limited variant of Advanced nanoparticles.
<u>Nanorod</u>	Builds a spherically-capped nanorod (FCC).
<u>Pentagonal nanorod</u>	Builds a pentagonal nanorod.
<u>Spherical molecular layer</u>	Builds atomic/molecular layers.
<u>Simple Crystal</u>	Builds an FCC lattice.

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Builder: Option list

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Table 1. Builder list and its description (continuation).

<u>R15 nanoparticles</u>	Builds nanoparticles using a particle radius of 15 Angstroms in custom position.
<u>Random Crystal</u>	Builds a multicomponent FCC lattice.
<u>Thinfilm (111)</u>	Generates "sc", "bcc", and "fcc" lattices and cleaves the crystals along a desired 111 plane.
<u>Thinfilm (hkl)</u>	Generates "sc", "bcc", and "fcc" lattices and cleaves the crystals along a desired hkl plane.
<u>WaterBox</u>	Builds water boxes.

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Builder: Advanced nanoparticles

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Metal System Builder for Molecular Dynamics Simulations

File Tabs Settings Help

Project Manager **Builder** Molecular Dynamics Analysis Terminal

>Select Builder<

Advanced nanoparticles [Ok]

>Advanced Nanoparticle builder<

Au

===> Lattice value
4.08

===> Total radius value
15

===> Shell radius value
5

===> Mol Fraction value
0.0

===> Vacancy percent
0.0

===> Vacancy inner radius
0.0

===> Vacancy outer radius
0.0

File Path

Using Molar Fraction [Make] [Run] [Finish]

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Builder: Advanced nanoparticles

File Manager

```
<OpenMD>
<MetaData>
  molecule{
    name = "Au";
    atom[0]{
      type = "Au";
      position(0+0, 0+0, 0+0);
    }
  }
  component{
    type = "Au";
    nMol = 1;
  }
}
```

Save file

Directory: /mnt/d/Onedrive/University/Investigation/DEV/OpenMD/Metals/Dime

AuNP_see.omd	dimethylmercury.omd	HgNP.omd	NPAuNP_see.omd
defaultName.sttd	dimethylmercury.report	HgNP.xyz	NPAuNP_see.report
default_sys.omd	dimethylmercury.stat	jspecview.properties	NPAuNP_see.stat
dimethylmercury.constraintForces	dimethylmercury.xyz	MetaData.md	NPAuNP_see.xyz
dimethylmercury.dump	gold.omd	NPAuNP_see.dump	
dimethylmercury.eor	Hg.omd	NPAuNP_see.eor	

File name: AdvAuNP.omd

Files of type: All Files (*)

Save Cancel

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Open file Save file Continue Exit

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Type file name

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Builder: Advanced nanoparticles

Metal System Builder for Molecular Dynamics Simulations

File Tabs Settings Help

Project Manager Builder Molecular Dynamics Analysis

> Select Builder <

Advanced nanoparticles

Ok

> Advanced Nanoparticle builder <

Bimetallic

====> Lattice value 4.08

====> Total radius value 15

====> Shell radius value 5

====> Mol Fraction value 0.0

====> Vacancy percent 0.0

====> Vacancy inner radius 0.0

====> Vacancy outer radius 0.0

Info

Result:
OpenMD info:
Removing 0 atoms from randomly-selected sites between 0.000000 and 0.000000.
Creating a core-shell spherical nanoparticle.
OpenMD info:
A new OpenMD file called "NPAdvAuNP.omd" has been generated.
Other errors: None

Ok

/mnt/d/Onedrive/University/Investigation/DEV/OpenMD/Atoms/DimethylHg/Topolog

Using Molar Fraction Make Run Finish

12

Metal System Builder for Molecular Dynamics Simulations

File Tabs Settings Help

Project Manager Builder Molecular Dynamics Analysis

> Select Builder <

Advanced nanoparticles

Ok

> Advanced Nanoparticle builder <

Bimetallic

====> Lattice value 4.08

====> Total radius value 15

====> Shell radius value 5

====> Mol Fraction value 0.0

====> Vacancy percent 0.0

====> Vacancy inner radius 0.0

====> Vacancy outer radius 0.0

File Path

/mnt/d/Onedrive/University/Investigation/DEV/OpenMD/Atoms/DimethylHg/Topolog

Using Molar Fraction Make Run Finish

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Builder: Convert structure

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Table 2. Input File Type support.

Table 2. Input File Type support.		

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Builder: Convert structure

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Builder: Convert structure

Select file path

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Builder: Dissolve solute

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Builder: Icosahedral nanoparticles

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Builder: Nanoparticles

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Builder: Nanoparticle with vacancy

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Builder: Nanorod

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Builder: Pentagonal nanorod

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Builder: Spherical molecular layer

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Builder: Simple Crystal

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Builder: R15 nanoparticles

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Builder: Random Crystal

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Builder:Thinfilm (111)

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Builder: Thinfilm (hkl)

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Builder: WaterBox

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Things to include in your portfolio

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Work samples

Use the work samples for a practical overview of demonstrated capabilities and expertise. Each example offers insights into various projects

Skills

Skills and qualifications are the credentials you have that show employers your experience and abilities in various areas that are related to your field

Professional narrative

An overview of past project successes or other accomplishments as well as a summary of relevant knowledge and skills gained over the course of your career

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John Doe

+34 654 321 432 | jane@freepik.com

"I always strive for **excellence**. I believe in the power of **collaboration**, and I love to build **meaningful relationships** with clients throughout the **creative process**"

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Now-20xx **Position A** Place A

- Describe your work tasks here
- Describe your work tasks here

20xx-20xx **Position B** Place B

- Describe your work tasks here
- Describe your work tasks here

20xx-20xx **Position C** Place C

- Describe your work tasks here
- Describe your work tasks here

Education

20xx-20xx **Studies 1**

- Competence
- Competence
- Competence

20xx-20xx **Studies 2**

- Competence
- Competence
- Competence

20xx-20xx **Studies 3**

- Competence
- Competence
- Competence

Cover letter

1 **Welcome to my portfolio!**

0

0 I'm [name], a highly creative and motivated individual, with a passion for [field
1 of expertise]. My portfolio is filled with unique and inspiring content, which
0 showcases my skills in the field.
1

0 Here you will find a lot of content that shows all my work. I strive for excellence
1 in all that I do, and this portfolio serves as a testament to my capabilities and
0 accomplishments.
0

1 Have a look around, get to know me better, and don't hesitate to reach out if
0 you have any questions or would like to collaborate!

1 Sincerely,
0

Slidesgo

+91 651 736 904

charlie@slidesgo.com

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Jane Doe

+91 620 421 838 | jane@freepik.com

Previous projects

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Project 1

“Explore the details of one of my previous projects, a testament to my ability to meet challenges head-on and deliver results. This undertaking reflects my approach to [industry/field] and highlights the diverse skills applied to ensure successful outcomes”

Project 2

“In this showcase of past projects, delve into another example that underscores my versatility and commitment to excellence. From concept to completion, witness how I navigated complexities and contributed to the success of this [industry/field] initiative”

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What people say about me

Employer 1

"I have been impressed by the quality, attention to detail and creative approach brought to every project made"

Employer 2

"This person's dedication and attention to detail significantly contributed to project success. Their creativity and ability to meet tight deadlines set them apart"

Employer 3

"This person has a strong technical understanding in order to develop successful strategies. Highly recommended for any kind of project or task"

Employer 4

"Working with this person has been valuable. Their strong work ethic and leadership qualities are instrumental in project success, combining a keen understanding of the bigger picture"

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My skills and qualifications

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Leadership

"I possess leadership abilities that have been sharpened through past roles where I was responsible for the teams"

Organization

"My proactivity allows me to plan ahead and prioritize tasks according to objectives and different deadlines"

Problem-solving

"My problem-solving capabilities have enabled me to solve difficult issues in the past, using creative and innovative solutions"

Technical skill

"I am knowledgeable in several technical areas that support my ambition in my field"

Communications

"With excellent verbal and written skills, I can effectively convey complex messages to a variety of audiences"

Interpersonal skill

"Teamwork is one of the essential part of my daily job, and I am sensitive towards different cultures"

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The number of projects I have
worked on so far

A chart of the areas I work in

- **Area 1**
Describe the area here
- **Area 2**
Describe the area here
- **Area 3**
Describe the area here
- **Area 4**
Describe the area here

Follow the link in the graph to modify its data and then paste the new one here. [For more info, click here](#)

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Table

	Project title	Skills	Date	Ref	Category	
1	Project 1	Describe the skills here	Jan 20XX	[Link or reference]	Write the category	1
0						0
0						1
1	Project 2	Describe the skills here	Feb 20XX	[Link or reference]	Write the category	0
0						0
1	Project 3	Describe the skills here	Mar 20XX	[Link or reference]	Write the category	0
0						1
0						0
1	Project 4	Describe the skills here	Apr 20XX	[Link or reference]	Write the category	0
0						1
1	Project 5	Describe the skills here	May 20XX	[Link or reference]	Write the category	0
0						1
1	Project 6	Describe the skills here	Jun 20XX	[Link or reference]	Write the category	0
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How did I achieve success?

Roadmap of my future projects

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Initiative	Objective	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Briefly describe the initiative 1	Describe the goal you want to achieve during the initiative	■	■										
Briefly describe the initiative 2	Describe the goal you want to achieve during the initiative		■	■	■								
Briefly describe the initiative 3	Describe the goal you want to achieve during the initiative				■	■	■						
Briefly describe the initiative 4	Describe the goal you want to achieve during the initiative						■	■	■				
Briefly describe the initiative 5	Describe the goal you want to achieve during the initiative								■	■	■		
Briefly describe the initiative 6	Describe the goal you want to achieve during the initiative										■	■	■

Thanks!

Do you have any questions?

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yourwebsite.com

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Alternative resources

Here's an assortment of alternative resources whose style fits that of this template:

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Did you like the resources used in this template? Get them on these websites:

Photos

- [Front view smiley man holding coffee cup](#)
- [Composition with html system for websites](#)
- [Composition with html system for websites I](#)
- [Html system for website concept](#)
- [Html system for websites concept](#)
- [Programming background with person working with codes on computer](#)
- [Programming background with person working with codes on computer](#)
- [Html and css collage concept with person](#)

Icons

- [Icon Pack: Programming | Lineal](#)

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Open Sans

(<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Open+Sans>)

Storyset

Create your Story with our illustrated concepts. Choose the style you like the most, edit its colors, pick the background and layers you want to show and bring them to life with the animator panel! It will boost your presentation. Check out [how it works](#).

Pana

Amico

Bro

Rafiki

Cuate

Use our editable graphic resources...

You can easily **resize** these resources without losing quality. To **change the color**, just ungroup the resource and click on the object you want to change. Then, click on the paint bucket and select the color you want. Group the resource again when you're done. You can also look for more **infographics** on Slidesgo.

...and our sets of editable icons

You can **resize** these icons without losing quality.

You can **change the stroke and fill color**; just select the icon and click on the **paint bucket/pen**.

In Google Slides, you can also use **Flaticon's extension**, allowing you to customize and add even more icons.

Educational Icons

Medical Icons

Business Icons

Teamwork Icons

Creative Process Icons

Performing Arts Icons

Nature Icons

SEO & Marketing Icons

